

INFLUENCE OF MOISTURE ABSORPTION ON HOT/WET COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF T800H/PMR-15 CARBON/POLYIMIDE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: Statistical compression tests for moisture absorbed specimens of a T800H/PMR-15 carbon/polyimide composite with a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence were conducted at 260°C. These tests clarified the compression fracture mode, the influence of moisture absorption on hot/wet compressive strength, statistical properties of hot/wet compressive strength, the effectiveness of a traveler coupon to monitor moisture absorption, and the relationship between specimen thickness and hot/wet compressive strength.

KEYWORDS: carbon/polyimide composite material, moisture absorption, hot/wet compressive strength, fracture mode, statistical features, traveler coupon, specimen thickness.

INTRODUCTION

The authors are conducting a series of reliability evaluation tests for the static strength of T800H/PMR-15 carbon/polyimide composite material. This material is a high temperature polymer composite to be applied to the tip fin and other secondary structures of the HOPE-X (H-II Orbiting PlanE), which is an experimental, unmanned, small space shuttle being jointly developed by the National Aerospace Laboratory (NAL), and National Space Development Agency (NASDA).

One of the most important mechanical properties in applying polymer composites to the space vehicle structures is hot/wet strength, especially hot/wet compressive strength. Many fundamental studies on carbon/polyimide composites and their applications were conducted and reported in Refs. 1 and 2. However, not much design data [1-4] has been published for these kinds of materials. The hot/wet tensile strength of polyimide composite materials is known to be fairly lower than that at room temperature, as reported in Ref. 3. However, no data of hot/wet compressive strength were found in Refs. 1 to 4. Moreover, statistical features of this property are not clarified for any carbon/polyimide materials, though this property is very important and expected to have a relatively large scatter.

This study investigated the influence of moisture absorption on hot/wet compressive strength and the distribution of hot/wet compressive strength of a T800H/PMR-15 carbon/polyimide composite. Static compression tests conducted at 260°C clarified the compressive failure mode, the influence of moisture absorption on hot/wet compressive strength, the statistical properties of hot/wet compressive strength, the effectiveness of a traveler coupon to monitor

the moisture content of a specimen tested, and the relationship between hot/wet compressive strength and specimen thickness.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN

The prepreg tape of T800H/PMR-15 carbon/polyimide was supplied by Yokohama Rubber Co. Laminate panels with a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence, 32 plies (45/0/-45/90)_{4s}, and coupon type specimens cut from these panels were made by Fuji Heavy Industries, Ltd. A specimen and a traveler coupon, i.e., an accompanied specimen, have the same configuration as illustrated in Fig. 1 and were not distinguished before a static test.

Fig. 1: Geometry of specimens and traveler coupons; dimensions in mm

MOISTURE ABSORPTION PROCESSING

Specimens were one by one sealed in a polyethylene bag and supplied to NAL. These specimens were moisturized by the following process. The moisture content of a specimen in this study was defined by that calculated from the weight change measured by a chemical balance.

Moisture Disorption Processing

At first specimens and traveler coupons were dried in a vacuum oven. Figure 2 presents the relationship between moisture disorption in weight percent and drying time in hours at 120°C. All specimens and traveler coupons were kept in the oven for 288 hours at 120°C. After this processing, the moisture contents of specimens and traveler coupons were defined to be zero percent.

Fig. 2: Moisture disorption in weight percent and drying time in hours at 120°C

Moisture Absorption Processing

Specimens and traveler coupons were soaked in a hot water bath for moisture absorption. The temperature of water was kept at 75°C. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship moisture absorption in weight percent and soaking time in hours. Since after 576 hours moisture absorption was considered to be saturated, the electric heater of the water bath was switched off. Specimens and traveler coupons were kept in this water bath in order to keep their moisture contents. However, this figure indicates the increase in the moisture content to about 1.8% after the stop of electricity. This phenomena seems to be generated because of the lower saturated vapor pressure inside of the specimen at room temperature than that at 75°C.

Fig. 3: Moisture absorption in weight percent versus soaking time in hours

The specimens in which the moisture content exceeds the required value were dried in the vacuum oven again. Then the moisture content was adjusted close to the required value by wrapping a specimen in wet tissue or drying it by an electric dryer. To investigate the statistical properties of hot/wet compressive strength, the water contents of 30 specimens and 30 traveler coupons before tests were controlled to be 1.2 weight percent as a target value. This target is 70% of the saturated moisture content, 1.7%, estimated in the planning stage of this study. The actually controlled values were from 1.19% to 1.24%. In addition, to know the effect for the large change of moisture content on the hot/wet compressive strength, three specimens and traveler coupons each were adjusted to about 1.78%, and the same number of specimens and traveler coupons were also adjusted to 1.35%.

COMPRESSION TEST PROCEDURE

Figure 4 shows the external appearance of the compression test fixture clamping a specimen and a traveler coupon placed beside the specimen. Compression tests were conducted at 260°C in an environmental chamber. This temperature is tentatively fixed as the upper limit of this material under mechanical loading for the structures of the HOPE-X. The temperatures of the specimen and the traveler coupon during a test were measured by thermocouples of a foil gage type installed to both surfaces of the specimen and to one surface of the traveler coupon. The temperature near the opening of the chamber from which hot air blew in was controlled at 295°C. When the lower temperature of those measured on the specimen reached 259°C, the compression test was started and finished under 261°C.

Heating a specimen up to 260°C and conducting the test were tried to be completed within 25 to 35 minutes. All the tests were finished within this time range after placing the compression

test fixture clamping a specimen on a test platen in the chamber. The average time was approximately 32 minutes. No preheating was given to the test fixture before clamping a specimen. Figure 5 indicates an example of temperature records of the specimen and traveler coupon. Since the traveler coupon was placed beside the specimen, the temperature of the traveler coupon rose faster than that of the specimen.

Specimens were evenly sampled from the location of the original laminate panels. A coupon adjacent to each specimen was selected as the traveler coupon in each test.

Fig. 4: External appearance of the compression test fixture clamping a specimen

Fig. 5: An example of temperature records of the specimen and traveler coupon during a hot/wet compression test

Compressive strength is represented by the nominal strength based on the nominal thickness. A digital servo-hydraulic testing machine was used for static tests. The speed of the actuator moving in a test was controlled at 1.3 mm/min.

Moisture content of the specimen and traveler coupon before and after a static test was obtained by measuring their weights. Their moisture content was not necessarily equal but very close. Not to disperse specimen debris, the testing machine was stopped by its limit function right after the specimen failed. This enabled an accurate measurement of the moisture content after the test.

TEST RESULTS

Relationship Between Compressive Strength and Temperature

Figure 6 illustrates the relationship between compressive strength and temperature. In these test results, the data of dry compressive strength obtained by the authors before this study were included.

This figure shows that the hot/wet compressive strength at 260°C is significantly lower than the dry compressive strength at 260°C; furthermore, on average, it is even lower than the dry compressive strength at 300°C.

Fig. 6: Compressive strength versus test temperature

Relationship Between Compressive Strength and Moisture Content

Figure 7 indicates the influence of moisture content on hot/wet compressive strength at 260°C. The compressive strength may have a weak correlation with the moisture content before the tests. However, a fairly clear correlation is recognized between the compressive strength and the moisture content after the tests, i.e., the residual moisture content. Therefore, it should be considered that the compressive strength has a strong and negative correlation with the residual moisture content. Moreover, this figure indicates that, if measurable, the moisture content of the specimen during static loading must be used. The specimen which showed the highest strength, about 350MPa, away from the group had an especially small residual moisture content. In this case the traveler coupon also had a very small moisture content after the test. Roughly a linear or semi-log linear line seems to be applicable to represent their relationship.

Fig. 7: Influence of moisture content on hot/wet compressive strength at 260°C

Most specimens indicated a shear fracture mode, that is, the specimen was obliquely broken on the side face. However, the specimen broken at the maximum strength showed a fracture mode of a rhombus shape as a side view dominantly caused by delamination. This fracture mode generally appears in a compression test at room temperature. This fact means that the fracture mode generally seen at room temperature appears when the residual moisture content is low enough and in such case the hot/wet compressive strength is restored. Therefore, the large reduction in hot/wet compressive strength can be prevented, if the residual moisture content is kept low enough to show the general fracture mode at room temperature. Figure 7 indicates that the fracture mode will change at around 0.6% of the residual moisture content.

Statistical Distribution of Hot/Wet Compressive Strength

Figure 8 illustrates the 30 observations of hot/wet compressive strength plotted on normal probability paper. These data were obtained by the specimens of which moisture content before the tests were adjusted to within 1.19 to 1.24%. Except for the value of the maximum strength, these data fit a normal distribution very well. As described above, the maximum strength is obtained by a different fracture mode. Therefore, this value should be removed from the data evaluated for structural design.

The mean hot/wet compressive strength is estimated to be 256 MPa from the censored data of a sample size of 29 on this probability paper. This value is approximately 53% of the mean dry compressive strength at 260°C in Fig. 6. The coefficient of variation as an index of data scatter is 8.9% and twice as large as that of the dry/room temperature compressive strength, obtained from a sample size of 30 [5]. This value is 2.5 times larger than that of dry compressive strength at 260°C, obtained from a sample size of 6.

Fig. 8: Hot/wet compressive strength distribution obtained by the specimens of which moisture contents were adjusted to within 1.19% to 1.24% before tests

Moisture Contents Before and After Test

Figure 9 illustrates the relationship between the moisture content before the test and that after the test separately for specimens and traveler coupons. It seems possible to control the residual moisture content, if only a small number of observations of large moisture contents before the tests were noticed. However, the residual moisture contents have a wide scatter of the moisture content controlled at about 1.2% in both cases of specimens and traveler coupons. For these data, no relation was recognized between the residual moisture content and the retention time from placing a specimen clamped by the test fixture on the test platen in the environmental chamber until the end of the test. This fact means that control of the residual moisture content is very difficult, though this content is deeply related with the hot/wet compressive strength as described above.

Fig. 9: Moisture contents before and after test for specimens and traveler coupons

Moisture Content Reductions of the Specimen and Traveler Coupon Used in the Same Test

The moisture content of a specimen or a product is generally estimated by that of a traveler coupon placed in the same environment in a practical process control. This method is

discussed here. Figure 10 presents the relationship between the moisture reduction of the specimen and that of the traveler coupon in the same test. Though the data points were expected to converge in a straight line, they are distributed in a wide band as shown in this figure. Therefore, to precisely estimate the moisture content by this method is impossible, but effective enough for a rough estimation.

Fig. 10: The relationship between the moisture reduction of the specimen and that of the traveler coupon in the same test

Fig. 11: Nominal hot/wet compressive strength versus measured specimen thickness

Relationship Between Hot/Wet Compressive Strength and Specimen Thickness

Specimens were machined from two panels cured at different times using the same cure condition. These specimens were separated from the original panels into two groups, called Batch A and Batch B. Figure 11 presents the relationship between nominal hot/wet compressive strength and measured specimen thickness, separated by each batch using different symbols. This figure shows that no correlation is recognized between hot/wet compressive strength and specimen thickness within this study.

CONCLUSIONS

The hot/wet compressive strength of the T800H/PMR-15 carbon/polyimide composite material was statistically investigated by static tests at 260°C. Major conclusions are as follows:

- (1) The fracture mode in most specimens is of shear fracture obliquely broken on the side face. However, at the maximum strength, a fracture mode of a rhombus shape as a side view, dominantly caused by delamination appeared, which is generally observed in a test at room temperature.
- (2) Hot/wet compressive strength was deeply related with the residual moisture content measured right after the test. When decreasing this content, the hot/wet compressive strength became higher.
- (3) The distribution form of the hot/wet compressive strength is approximated well with a normal distribution except for the maximum strength. The mean and coefficient of variation should be estimated from this censored distribution.
- (4) The mean hot/wet compressive strength of specimens absorbing moisture of 1.19 to 1.24 weight % before tests decreased to 53% of that of dry specimens at 260°C.
- (5) The coefficient of variation of hot/wet compressive strength was approximately twice as large as that of room temperature/dry compressive strength.
- (6) Control of the residual moisture content was considered difficult.
- (7) The traveler coupon used to monitor the moisture content of the specimen in the same test is effective only for a rough estimation, but is difficult for an accurate estimation.
- (8) No strong correlation was found between hot/wet compressive strength and specimen thickness.

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